

Ideas on Authenticating Humanness in Collaborative Systems Using AI-Hard Problems in Perception and Cognition

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Abstract—Collaborative applications including email, chat, file-sharing networks, blogs, and gaming are under constant threat of automated programs that are gaining access to, attacking, degrading, or otherwise disrupting the intended communications and interactions. Thus, an important issue in collaborative systems security is how to verify that a user is a human, and not a computer attempting to access the system for malicious purposes. We propose and discuss several AI-hard examples from perception and cognition that may be useful for distinguishing between human-level intelligence and artificial intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Attempts at distributed collaboration are often hampered by automated computer programs intentionally wreaking havoc within the collaborative system. On-line gaming is plagued by cheating computer programs. The integrity of all on-line polls is questionable given the possibility of automated voting programs skewing the results. Email systems, blogs, and file-sharing networks are inundated by the spam generated by automated programs. Further, sophisticated “chat-bots” equipped with artificial intelligence (AI) can pose as humans to gather personal information, using social engineering techniques on an unprecedented scale [1]. Incidentally, there are also a variety of other non-collaborative situations in which automated programs can threaten the security of a system (e.g., repetitious dictionary attacks on password protected systems; denial-of-service attacks; etc.). Thus, the seemingly philosophical question of how to distinguish between people and computers has very real implications for collaborative technologies and computer security.

II. TURING TESTS, HIPs, AND CAPTCHAS

Any automated test or method of distinguishing between people and computers is called a Reverse Turing Test (RTT), a Human Interaction Proof (HIP), an Automated Turing Test (ATT), or a Completely Automated Public Turing Test to Tell Computers and Humans Apart (CAPTCHA) [2,3,4]. The fact

that the test is *automated* means that it is presented and graded by a computer. This is in contrast to the original Turing Test proposed by Alan Turing in the 1950’s, in which humans attempt to determine whether they are communicating (typing back-and-forth) with another human, or with a computer posing as a human [5]. Reliable automated methods can limit access to collaborative and distributed network systems to only users that are verifiably human, thereby avoiding a significant range of potential security and usability problems.

A. AI-Hard Problems and CAPTCHA Development

The most effective CAPTCHAs seem to be the ones that pose AI-hard problems to the test-takers. “AI-hard” problems are informally the most difficult problems facing the artificial intelligence community [6]. Solving these problems using automated programs seems to require computational abilities comparable to or exceeding human-level intelligence. Therefore, these problems provide a way of challenging a test-taker so that only a human can easily solve them, while a computer cannot. And the security or “hardness” of the test is guaranteed as long as the problem domain remains generally unsolvable by computer. Listed below are some other desirable characteristics of CAPTCHA tests [4,7]:

- The tests are easy for people to pass, but difficult for computers. “Easy” tests for people means not too time-consuming or complex.
- Tests should be passable by the vast majority of humans, including young and old, the physically-impaired, etc.
- Tests should be as culturally-independent, language-independent, and background-independent as possible.
- Tests should be resistant to repeated random guessing by computer; large numbers of multiple-choice questions may be used in this regard, and/or multiple

sequentially-presented successful trials are required to pass the test.

- Tests should be resistant to template-matching; i.e., test stimuli might need to be varied on each presentation to avoid a computer recognizing and cataloguing questions or stimuli after repeated attempts.
- Test *presentation* and *grading* is automated; i.e., performed by computer.

If *generating* tests can also be automated, it removes the need for large databases of catalogued stimuli. Databases of stimuli can be problematic for security, especially if the database is publicly available, as these can be broken with assistance from large groups of people. It is not unthinkable that a database of 1 million CAPTCHA photos, for example, can be catalogued by workers solving each test for 1 cent per test; in this manner, the entire database of 1 million images can be broken with only \$10,000.

B. Current CAPTCHAs

The CAPTCHAs that are currently in widespread use are almost uniformly based upon the AI-hard problem of text readability. The concept, referred to as “pessimal print,” prompts a test-taker with a series of visually-presented letters and/or numbers that are randomly distorted (see Fig. 1). The test-taker must correctly type the presented letters/numbers before being granted access to the protected system. The visual distortions are intended to foil Optical Character Recognition algorithms so that only humans can correctly type the passcode and gain access to the system [2].

Object recognition in static imagery is another CAPTCHA gaining widespread interest [4]. One version of this test might require users to identify a single object from a series of different imagery. This CAPTCHA method exploits the AI-hard problem of object recognition, a capability in which humans (currently) excel relative to computers.

III. CAPTCHA PROPOSALS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The problem with many current CAPTCHAs is that they are rapidly becoming vulnerable to improvements in AI, particularly the tests involving text-readability [8,9]. Thus, there is a pressing need to develop more advanced CAPTCHAs that will remain invulnerable to AI attack for a relatively longer time. In this work, we will discuss several AI-hard perceptual and cognitive problems from the psychological literature and their potential implementations as CAPTCHAs. We hope that these ideas may prove useful in the growing battle to distinguish people from computers.

A. Facial Feature Recognition

Face recognition is a remarkable human ability that is currently problematic for computers to emulate. Humans have a dedicated region of brain tissue devoted exclusively to processing facial feature information [10], and they are extremely good at it, despite variations in image lighting, angle, distance, shape, color, and the presence of facial hair,

glasses, hats, etc. While there have been many advances in this field in regards to AI, the task remains exceedingly difficult for computers to perform reliably due to the unavoidable variations in facial imagery mentioned [11].

A CAPTCHA based on the AI-hard principle of face recognition might present users a large number of photos, of which only two photos are of a single person. The photos are numbered, and the test-taker must identify the pair that goes together by typing in the correct numbers (see Fig. 2). This type of CAPTCHA should be difficult to break using a computer algorithm, and should also be resistant to guessing. Although there are only 8 photos, there are 28 possible photo pairs to choose from, making the chances of randomly guessing the correct pair on a single test 3.57%. If multiple correct responses are required before gaining admission to the system, the odds of guessing twice in a row becomes 0.13%, and the odds of guessing three times in a row becomes less than 0.01%. A potentially negative aspect of this type of CAPTCHA implementation, however, is that it would require a database of catalogued imagery to be drawn upon.

Rui & Liu [7] have proposed a face-based CAPTCHA called ARTiFACIAL, which presents users with a cluttered, distorted image consisting of a variety of facial features (eyes, noses, mouths, etc.), which appear to be haphazardly scattered around the image. Users must find the single “correctly” organized face in this clutter and click on 6 points (two eye corners and two mouth corners) to signal the identification of a face. They found that humans could complete the task in under 15 seconds with a success rate of 99.7%, while several face detection algorithms could rarely find the face, and even when found, a feature detection algorithm could only locate all six points 0.2% of the time.

Figure 1. Example of a Pessimal Print CAPTCHA.

Figure 2. Example of a Face Recognition CAPTCHA. Images 4 and 6 are of the same individual.

Although facial recognition algorithms cannot currently compare to a human’s ability, significant progress is being made in both facial and object recognition, the latter of which will no doubt improve facial recognition since both fields rely on similar image processing principles and techniques. Any improvement over random guessing, even if performance is not perfect, can spell trouble for CAPTCHA security. So other more difficult CAPTCHAs might soon be necessary.

B. Motion Perception

Motion perception is a computationally difficult problem to solve, but is easy for humans, and so is a natural possibility for a potential CAPTCHA. Indeed, a CAPTCHA based on the AI-hard task of complex motion perception has already been proposed [12]. This proposal utilizes foreground typographical characters moving against a background of visual clutter, with the movement driven by the interaction of the user. Also proposed is the display of a video clip, whereby certain questions relating to the content of the video are asked, requiring reading of typographical passcodes present in the video, or typing short descriptions of the video. A potential shortcoming of this first idea is that at its core, the test is still based strongly on text readability that happens to be dynamic, although it is certainly a step in the right direction. Some potential problems with the second idea is that generating or grading textual descriptions of complex video scenes cannot be easily automated, so large databases of catalogued video clips would be necessary for implementation.

To overcome some of these issues with a motion-based CAPTCHA, we have several different proposals. First, one might use a dynamic visual search task, in which a single moving target is sought amongst an array of visually distracting objects that are also in motion. All objects could be moving on different trajectories, and the task would prompt the user to search for a target with specific features (for instance, large, blue, and square). The distracting objects might vary in size, color, and/or shape. Once the target is found, the participant must signal the direction that the target is moving (perhaps using a dial or other radial control). This proposed CAPTCHA would benefit from being easy to generate and grade the tests using a computer, and would additionally combine two AI-hard tasks into one (object recognition and motion perception), increasing its strength.

A second idea might be to utilize the perceptual phenomenon of *form-from-motion*. Similar to point-light displays, form-from-motion perception is the ability to discern “objectness” in an apparently random field of dots, as long as the dots are in motion, and are moving as if they spots of light atop of objects. In other words, any static scene of the dots gives no clue as to object structure, but motion of the dots in the appropriate manner gives rise to the perception of an object in the scene. Due to the sparseness of the visual information, and the computational complexity necessary for object recognition, it is certainly an AI-hard problem. Indeed, it sometimes used as a neuropsychological test to assess brain damage [e.g., see 13]. In this proposal, a standard set of catalogued virtual objects would need to exist, but 2D and 3D graphics engines could easily allow randomization of the dot placements, and variations in rotation/viewpoint/type of

Figure 3. Example of a Depth Perception CAPTCHA utilizing occlusion depth cues. Correct depth-ordering of these objects, from nearest to farthest, is 1-4-6-2-5-3.

motion would remove the need for a fixed database of tests that might be broken by brute force human assistance.

C. Depth Perception

Monocular depth perception via two-dimensional displays (also called 2½ D, pictorial, or perspective depth) is an amazing human capability that has consistently resisted computational replication, i.e., it is an AI-hard problem. Again, humans generally find this task easy and natural, suggesting a further possibility for a future CAPTCHA. A blogger [14] has already designed a 3D CAPTCHA based on this principle. In his implementation, a user would view a 3D representation of an animal from a particular viewpoint (e.g., a rabbit viewed from the side). Then, the user views a grid of several images of different virtual animals taken from varying viewpoints. The user must match the first image with its corresponding image in the grid (e.g., a rabbit viewed from the back, and from above). The fact that the stimuli are images of virtual objects allows the tests to be easily presented and tested by computer, although a stored database of 3D representations seems necessary. This sort of implementation could be hardened against random guessing by using large number of test images for the grid, and/or by requiring multiple sequential correct answers before authentication is granted. A somewhat related proposal for a 3D object recognition CAPTCHA is given by Kaplan [15].

In addition to focusing upon virtual 3D object recognition, we propose other depth perception CAPTCHAs that focus on depth ordering and/or depth judgments. Such a test might present a single computer-generated image in which a variety of different labeled objects appear at varying depths. Any of the monocular cues to depth, including relative size, texture, occlusion, linear perspective, shadows, etc. might be utilized. The test might ask users to type in the order in which the objects appear, from nearest to farthest (see Fig. 3); or users might have to answer a series of questions about relative depth orders, such as whether one shape appears in front of another. If the depth ordering task requires the correct ordering of only 6 objects, the odds of a random guess being correct are 0.14%, making this type of CAPTCHA extremely hardened against random guess attacks.

Figure 4. Example of a Mental Rotation CAPTCHA. The reference object (on the left) must be matched with its rotated counterpart (object C).

D. Mental Rotation

Mental rotation tasks have been used in psychology for decades to assess mental functioning and to test theories about cognition [16]. Mental rotation in humans is made possible through the use of a visuo-spatial “sketchpad” or “scratchpad” upon which a mental representation of an object is spatially rotated [17]. Programs lacking similar computational abilities should be unable to correctly complete these tasks, suggesting another possible CAPTCHA test.

In a potential mental rotation CAPTCHA, a three-dimensional reference object (perhaps made up of individual blocks, such as those used in [16]) would be presented to users. Then, several test objects could be shown, only one of which is identical to the reference object but rotated in three dimensions (see Fig. 4). It is recommended that 3D rotations be used, as 2D rotations would likely be vulnerable to simple template-matching hacks. Indeed, this idea is nearly identical to the 3D animal CAPTCHA discussed earlier [14], although that implementation used familiar animals as opposed to simple objects, so was more analogous to object recognition than object matching. Our idea potentially benefits from the fact that a stored database of 3D representations is not necessary, as the 3D shapes could be generated on-the-fly. However, matching a randomly shaped object to its rotated counterpart seems to require more cognitive effort than recognizing familiar animals viewed from different perspectives. So our proposal would probably utilize a smaller number of test objects per trial to allow for easy human use, which unfortunately could increase the chances of successful random guessing. Multiple sequential testing might therefore be necessary to minimize this problem.

E. Categorization and Rule-Learning

Categorization and rule-learning tasks are used often by neuropsychologists to assess mental functioning by testing attention, working memory, reasoning, problem-solving, and visual processing [e.g., 18]. Due to the cognitive complexity of such tasks, they might be especially useful as CAPTCHAs. In addition, computerized versions of these tests already exist that can easily generate, present, and score the tests.

For instance, the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST) [19] first displays to participants several example cards, consisting of different combinations of numbers, colors, and shapes of symbols on each card (somewhat like a standard 52-card deck of playing cards). The few visible example cards are pre-sorted according to a rule unknown to the participant. The participant must then sort the remaining deck of cards by

Figure 5. Example of a CAPTCHA requiring Categorization and/or Rule-learning. Each card must be matched to its pair based on ambiguous rules of “similarity” or group-membership.

attempting to guess the sorting rule, which can change at any time. The test administrator (or computer) simply says “Correct” or “Incorrect” in response to each sorting attempt. Performance is assessed by seeing how long it takes to figure out the sorting rule, how long to figure out if the rules have changed, how long to learn new rules, and the number and type of mistakes made while sorting [18]. As a potential CAPTCHA, such a test would need to be shorter than normal (the standard WCST can take up to 20 minutes), and might require different scoring methods and/or different visual stimuli than simple colored shapes, to avoid template matching by computer.

Another potential CAPTCHA based on a similar principle could be implemented like the game Memory®. In this game, cards are arranged face-down on a grid. Participants must select two cards at a time to view and attempt to remember their identities and spatial locations. The object is to find and select the matching pair cards on the same turn, so that matching pairs remain face up the remainder of the game. When all pairs have been found, and all cards are face up, the game is complete. Difficulty may be added to this game by defining “pairs” of cards according to higher-level categories, instead of requiring simple image matching as in the original game. For instance, pairs might be defined by membership in a group, such as four-digit numbers, vowels, faces of women, faces of children, objects used for cleaning, vehicles used for transportation, etc. (see Fig. 5). In this manner, similar to the WCST, the player must learn the “rules” by which cards are grouped so that the correct matches can be found.

Such an implementation might require a large database of catalogued stimuli, but due to its higher-level cognitive nature, it would be difficult to break computationally, and would be very resistant against random guessing. If the difficulty for humans of remembering the spatial locations of cards is too cumbersome, the test can be administered with all cards facing up, which is a similar idea as that used in the CAPTCHA program *Bongo* [4]. Admission to the system would be granted after correct sequential clicking of the image pairs. The odds of randomly guessing the correct pairings with no mistakes for a game with 5 pairs (10 cards) would be only 0.11%.

F. Spatial (3D) Audio

There is increasing interest in CAPTCHAs based on auditory challenges, so that visually-impaired test-takers will not be unfairly excluded [4]. Some auditory CAPTCHAs are in current use, but like pessimal print, they are at risk of being broken by advancing AI (pattern recognition, natural language processing, etc.). Therefore, more advanced auditory CAPTCHAs are also needed.

Spatial hearing is a complex and impressive human capability that might serve as a useful CAPTCHA test. A test based on virtual audio (also called “spatial” or “3D” audio) can create the truly compelling illusion of a sound or sounds coming from particular directions in space. In terms of hardware, a spatial hearing challenge would only require the user to possess a stereo sound card and a pair of stereo headphones. Participants might have to signal the direction of a target sound, or perhaps listen for a passcode coming from any direction, all in the presence of a spatially noisy virtual environment. A computer program lacking complex binaural sound processing and natural language processing should have great difficulty in passing such 3D sound tests. Additionally, such tests should be extremely easy for most humans and should be very difficult to solve through random guessing.

IV. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

The proposed CAPTHCAs discussed above benefit from being cognitively complex tasks that are currently easy for humans to solve, but difficult for computers. We attempted to propose tests that should be relatively simple to generate, present, and grade by computer; i.e., they are “automated” tests. Indeed, since most of these tests are based upon cognitive phenomena that have been studied by psychologists and others for decades, automated versions of many of them already exist. Additionally, care was taken in the selection of these tasks to ensure that they would be relatively usable for most people (quick and not too difficult). Since these tests are based around *general* cognitive and perceptual tests, they should be essentially language, background, and culture independent.

We also took care in proposing tests that would be mostly resistant to random guess attacks (by using multiple test stimuli or using sequential testing trials) and to template-matching hacks (by randomizing test stimuli before presentation). However, potentially the biggest threat to any CAPTCHA seems unavoidable, regardless of the particular test used: human assistance. As mentioned earlier, any time a bot runs up against a CAPTCHA it cannot solve, nothing seems to be able to stop the bot from sending the problem (or problems) to a bank of human operators providing assistance, who can send the solution back to the bot thus gaining access to the restricted system. The best conceivable option appears to be to develop a CAPTCHA that is difficult or time-consuming enough to make paying for human assistance too expensive, while not too difficult or time-consuming to drive away non-malicious users.

The ability to reliably distinguish people from computers is an extremely important issue for the security of many modern network platforms, particularly those platforms

involving collaboration and distributed communications. File-sharing networks, email systems, social networks, chat-rooms, blogs, webpages, online voting, and multi-player gaming are some of the collaborative applications that are especially vulnerable to automated computer malfeasance. We have discussed several outstanding AI-hard problems in perception and cognition that we believe hold particular promise as CAPTCHAs, for the purposes of developing tests capable of reliably distinguishing between humans and computers. The well-grounded fields of testing of perceptual and cognitive function (psychology, neuropsychology) and attempting to replicate these functions (cognitive science) have been largely unapplied to the related question of verifying humanness in computer systems (computer science). We hope to remedy this situation by providing further ideas and exploring new avenues of research into the important question of how to automate human authentication via computer, with the ultimate goal of ensuring the security and usability of collaborative and distributed network systems.

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